

Influence of preparation procedure on the conductivity and transparency of SWCNT-polymer nanocomposites

J.J. Hernández¹, M.C. García-Gutiérrez^{1*}, A. Nogales¹, D.R. Rueda¹, M. Kwiatkowska²,
A. Szymczyk², Z. Roslaniec², A. Concheso³, I. Guinea³, T.A. Ezquerra¹

¹ Instituto de Estructura de la Materia, CSIC, Serrano 121, 28006 Madrid, Spain

² Technical University of Szczecin , Institute of Materials Science and Engineering,
Piastrów Av. 19, PL-70310 Szczecin, Poland

³ Grupo Antolín Ingeniería, Ctra. Irún 244, E-09007 Burgos, Spain

Nanostructuring of polymers has opened up new perspectives for multi-functional materials. In this paper we report on the feasibility of preparing transparent and conducting polymer nanocomposites based on poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) as additive. Polymer nanocomposites were prepared by two different methods, direct mixing in the melt (DM) and in-situ polymerization (I-SP). Samples prepared by DM show a low percolation threshold for electric conductivity, $\phi_c = 0.024$ wt % of SWCNT, and are more transparent to light than samples prepared by I-SP. Particularly, a DM composite with composition just above ϕ_c exhibits a conductivity of $\sim 10^{-8}$ S/cm and about 70% of transmittance to visible light. Better electrical and optical properties of nanocomposites prepared by DM in relation to those prepared by I-SP can be explained by assuming that a certain level of aggregation of SWCNT favors the formation of electrical pathways and reduces the number of scatters of light, hence favoring the transmittance of the visible light through these materials.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes; Polymer nanocomposites; Electrical conductivity; Transparency

1. Introduction

Single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) have attracted much attention since their discovery. Their exceptional mechanical, electrical, thermal properties and high aspect ratio make them excellent candidates as fillers in multifunctional nanocomposites.

Because of van der Waals attraction among nanotubes and their large surface areas, SWCNT tend to form agglomerates which prevent from an efficient transfer of their superior properties to the nanocomposite. Therefore, the nanotube dispersion in the polymer matrix is a big concern. As reported by some authors [1] the existence of fractal morphology of branched agglomerates of SWCNT has significant negative impact on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite material. However, as far as the electrical properties are concerned, the impact of aggregation on the mechanisms of percolation, the so called static and kinetic percolation and on the electrical conductivity are still under investigation [2]. It has been reported that the onset of the conductivity in CNT nanocomposites is closely related to the aggregation level of the conducting nanotubes [3]. Agglomeration of nanotubes, rather than a simple random arrangement of isolated elements, appears to improve the efficiency of the conducting network. [4].

Thin laminated indium tin oxide (ITO) is the industry standard material to provide optically transparent electrical conductivity to glass and polymeric films. However, there are still several disadvantages such as possible delamination of ITO film, a relatively high processing temperature, fabrication costs, and so on [5]. An alternative to ITO is offered by conducting composites based on carbon nanotubes. This goal is not a trivial matter, given the high optical absorption of carbon nanotubes. Due

to this effect only few works have been reported on this topic, either concerning thin coatings on transparent substrates [6, 7] or carbon nanotube networks based on electrophoretic deposition [8, 9] using non standard processing methods whit several steps. From an industrial point of view, direct mixing of carbon nanotubes in the polymer melt is one of the most desirable methods for producing conductive and transparent polymer nanocomposites in the bulk. The properties, low cost and processing advantages of these materials would find use in a wide variety of applications such as microelectronics, EMI shielding and large area displays [10, 11], among others.

The aim of this study is to compare the optical and electrical properties of nanocomposite films based on poly(ethylene terephthalate) and single wall carbon nanotubes, obtained by two different methods of great interest from an industrial point of view: direct mixing of carbon nanotubes in the molten polymer (DM) and in-situ polymerization (I-SP).

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

Nanocomposites based on poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and single-wall carbon nanotubes (CNI Technology Co., TX, USA, synthesized by using the HiPco[®] method) several microns length and about 1.4 nm in diameter, as revealed by Raman spectroscopy [12], were prepared by two different procedures.

Direct mixing (DM): The nanocomposites were prepared by mixing the nanoadditive with PET (Rhodia S80 from RhodiaSter, $M_v = 45,000$ g/mol) in the molten state. Selected amounts of SWCNT were added to the polymer melt ($T = 280$ °C) while stirring at 100 rpm the mixture during about 5 min at maximum torque of 3.6 N

m. An internal mixer Microcompounder from DACA instruments (Goleta CA93116) was used. Different nanocomposites with SWCNT weight concentration between 0% and 5% were obtained.

In-situ polymerization (I-SP): A similar procedure was used as that previously described for poly(butylene terephthalate)[14]. A selected amount of SWCNT was dispersed by ultrasonication and high-speed stirring in ethylene glycol (BASF, Germany). The SWCNT dispersion along with dimethyl terephthalate (Elana S.A., Torun, Poland) was introduced in an acid-resistant steel reactor where takes place the polycondensation by transesterification between both ethylene glycol and dimethyl terephthalate. The nanocomposite was extruded from the reactor using compressed nitrogen. Nanocomposites with SWCNT weight concentration between 0% and 0.3% were obtained. The measured molecular weight of the PET matrix is $M_w \approx 27,600$ g/mol. Films of nanocomposites (about 250 μm thick) were prepared by compression molding at 285 °C for 3 minutes, and subsequently quenched in ice-water.

2.2. Broad band electrical conductivity

Circular gold electrodes (20 mm in diameter) were deposited onto the surfaces of the sample film. The complex permittivity $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$, where ϵ' represents the permittivity and ϵ'' the dielectric loss, of the nanocomposites was measured as a function of frequency ($10^{-1} \text{ Hz} < F < 10^6 \text{ Hz}$, being F the frequency of the applied electric field) and temperature (-150 °C up to 150 °C) by using a Novocontrol broadband dielectric spectrometer. Temperature control was obtained by a nitrogen jet (QUATRO from Novocontrol) with a temperature error, during every single sweep in frequency, of 0.1 K. Electrical conductivity was derived by $\sigma(F) = \epsilon_o 2\pi F \epsilon''$ where ϵ_o is the vacuum permittivity.

2.3. Optical transparency

The transmittance of the films was determined by a Haze-gard plus (BYK-Gardner) equipment, under the standard form ASTM D1003-95 “Standard Test Method for Haze and Luminous Transmittance of Transparent Plastics”.

2.4. Structural characterization

Both, nanocomposites prepared by direct mixing of carbon nanotubes in the molten polymer (DM) and those prepared by in-situ polymerization (I-SP), have been characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were cryofractured in liquid nitrogen, and then vacuum coated with a thin gold film before being analyzed using a JEOL JSM-6100 Scanning Electron Microscope.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Structure and morphology of nanocomposites

The morphology of the SWCNT (as received) used in this study is shown in Figure 1. According to the SEM micrograph it is clear that the nanoadditive consists of a branched network formed by the characteristic ropes of nanotubes. In a previous work [13] we have demonstrated that for nanocomposites prepared by mixing the nanotubes in the molten polymer matrix the shear forces are not enough to break the rope morphology. Therefore the resulting morphology retains an aggregate morphology as shown by SAXS experiments.

Over the last five years, in-situ polymerization in the presence of carbon nanotubes has been intensively explored for the preparation of polymer-grafted nanotubes and processing of the corresponding polymer-composite materials. The main

advantage of this method is that it enables a better nanotube dispersion and formation of a strong interface between the nanotube and the polymer matrix [1, 14].

Figure 2 shows SEM micrographs of: (a) nanocomposite prepared by direct mixing 0.2% wt of SWCNT in the molten polymer (DM) and (b) nanocomposite prepared by in-situ polymerization (I-SP) with 0.3% wt of SWCNT. Comparing both micrographs it seems that nanotubes are slightly better dispersed in the I-SP nanocomposite because the nanotubes ropes are isolated and homogeneously distributed in this case, while for the DM nanocomposite the ropes of nanotubes are in some extent agglomerated.

It is known that PET can become a semicrystalline polymer depending on the quenching conditions when cooling from the melt [15]. In addition, it has been reported that CNT act as nucleation agent fastening the crystallization kinetics of the polymer matrix [16, 17]. The samples investigated in this work have been characterized by wide angle X-ray scattering, showing that the nanocomposite films are mainly amorphous and therefore polymer crystals will not contribute to their electrical and optical properties.

3.2 Electrical conductivity

Figure 3 shows the electrical conductivity, $\sigma(F)$ as a function of frequency for nanocomposites with different weight concentration of SWCNT, prepared by DM (upper) and by I-SP (bottom). For nanoadditive concentrations below 0.02 wt %, $\sigma(F)$ follows a linear dependence with frequency with a slope close to 1, which is characteristic of insulating materials. This behavior is also observed for the PET matrix. However, for concentrations equal or higher than 0.05 wt % of SWCNT, $\sigma(F)$ adopts a

characteristic behavior which can be formally depicted by the so called universal dynamic response [18, 19] described by a law of the type:

$$\sigma(F) = \sigma_{dc} + \sigma_{ac} = \sigma_{dc} + A \cdot F^S \quad (1)$$

where σ_{dc} is the frequency independent direct current conductivity and $0 < S < 1$. This law introduces a critical frequency, F_c , above which $\sigma(F) = \sigma_{ac} \propto F^S$.

Figure 4 represents the σ_{dc} data (the value of the conductivity at the lowest measured frequency, 10^{-1} Hz, has been considered as σ_{dc} for comparative purpose) as a function of wt% concentration of the nanoadditive for the two systems investigated. It seems that the nanocomposites prepared by DM exhibit slightly higher conductivity values than those of the nanocomposites prepared by I-SP (see inset). In both cases, a characteristic percolative behavior is observed. For SWCNT low concentrations, the conductivity remains at the same level than the insulating matrix. At a certain critical concentration, ranging between 0.02 wt % and 0.05 wt %, the conductivity starts a sudden increase.

The dc conductivity above the critical concentration can be analyzed in terms of the percolation theory [20, 21] by means of the scaling law given by:

$$\sigma_{dc} = \sigma_0 (\phi - \phi_c)^t \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 is a scaling factor that is comparable to the effective conductivity of the filler [22], ϕ is the weight fraction of nanotubes, ϕ_c is the percolation critical concentration above which the material behaves like a conductor and below which the material behaves like an insulator, and t is a critical exponent, which depends on the dimensionality of the system [20, 21].

Theoretical calculations [20, 21], supported by a great amount of experimental observations in both, composites with either isotropic additives [23] or with fiber like additives [3, 24, 25] propose t values between 1.6 and 2 for random three dimensional

systems. The fitting of eq. 2 to the experimental data of Fig. 4 provides t values of 1.79 and 1.87 with $\phi_c = 0.024$ wt % and $\phi_c = 0.048$ wt % for nanocomposites prepared by DM and prepared by I-SP, respectively. The t values obtained are in reasonable agreement with the theoretical value for a three-dimensional percolating network. Both percolation thresholds (ϕ_c) are quite low compared to values reported in the literature for polymer nanocomposites based on SWCNT, produced either from a solvent-based solution or from a polymer melt [26-29], and even for those nanocomposites produced by more laborious methods: combination of polymer emulsion and water-based SWCNT stabilized suspensions [7, 30, 31], functionalization of SWCNT providing solubilization in organic solvents that allows homogeneous dispersions of nanotubes in the polymer matrix [4, 32], coagulation methods [33], among others. A classification of percolating materials considering statistical and kinetic percolation has been recently proposed [2]. Here statistical percolation refers to a situation where randomly distributed fillers form percolating paths and kinetic percolation is attributed to the case where particle movement and re-aggregation is allowed. Our results could be considered as a particular case of kinetic percolation in the sense that neither for DM nanocomposites nor for I-SP materials the complete rupture of SWCNT ropes is achieved. This fact implies a low value of the percolation threshold as stated in reference [2]. Nevertheless, the percolation threshold (ϕ_c) of the nanocomposite prepared by in-situ polymerization is above twice the value of the percolation threshold reached by preparing the nanocomposite by direct mixing in the melt. This trend is consistent with the idea that the onset of conductivity in CNT based nanocomposites is not a purely geometrical problem concerning the aspect ratio of individual fillers, but it is closely related to the aggregation level of the conducting nanotubes [2, 3, 4, 6]. As it has been mentioned in section 3.1 nanocomposites prepared by mixing the nanotubes in

the molten polymer matrix, present larger agglomeration of nanotubes which retain the rope morphology inherent to the self assembling nature of raw SWCNT (Fig. 1) due to van der Waals attraction between nanotubes. This supports that a certain degree of aggregation, rather than a simple random arrangement of nanotubes, encourages percolation.

3.3 Transparent conductors

Figure 5 compares the transparency of two nanocomposite films with similar thickness and composition (0.1 wt% of SWCNT) prepared by DM (left side) and by I-SP (right side), placed over 1€ coin. While the sample prepared by DM allows seeing the coin behind, the sample prepared by I-SP does not.

In order to get a quantitative comparison of the optical properties of composites, the optical transmittance has been measured for the two series of nanocomposites. The transmittance is the intensity ratio between the transmitted and the incident light (I_t/I_o). In Table 1 are listed the thicknesses of both series of nanocomposites. Figure 6 shows how the transmittance abruptly decreases with increasing SWCNT content for both series. A transmittance of about 90 % is observed for the two PET matrices. It is remarkable the differences observed in transmittance for samples with similar composition being samples prepared by DM much more transparent than samples prepared by I-SP as was also illustrated in Fig. 5.

In Figure 7 we have represented the experimental values of the optical transmittance versus the logarithm of the electrical conductivity for the two series of nanocomposites. In addition it is plotted the values of conductivity ($\sim 10^{-8}$ S/cm) and transmittance (about 69 %) derived from the results of Fig. 4 and Fig. 6 respectively, for

a nanocomposite prepared by DM with composition the percolation critical concentration ($\phi_c = 0.024$ wt % of SWCNT).

It is well known that the presence of micro-heterogeneities in a material i.e. dust in air, crystals in semicrystalline polymers, or additives in polymer composites, etc perturb the linear transmission of light throughout it because of scattering of light. As a result the transmitted light in the direction of the incoming light source is severely reduced depending mainly on the heterogeneities concentration (number of light scatters). We think that the different transmittance observed for the two nanocomposites investigated should be attributed to differences in the dispersion of SWCNT achieved. Then, the lower transparency of nanocomposites prepared by I-SP is supporting a better dispersion of nanoadditive (higher number of light scatters) in the polymer matrix in relation to the more transparent nanocomposites prepared by DM (lower number of light scatters). This assumption agrees with the higher transparency reached by electric field-induced aligned MWCNT networks in epoxy composites compared to random networks of similar systems, fact that is also explained considering the reduction of independent scattering centers after agglomeration of CNT due to the alignment by the electric field [34].

4. Conclusions

The electrical and optical properties of polymer nanocomposites (PET/SWCNT) prepared by two different methods, direct mixing and in-situ polymerization were investigated. Materials prepared by DM with a low percolation threshold for electric conductivity, ($\phi_c = 0.024$ wt% of SWCNT) show a transmittance to light of about 70% just above the critical concentration ϕ_c . Nanocomposites prepared by I-SP with similar or lower levels of conductivity are much less transparent to light than DM

nanocomposites. Such differences suggest that a certain level of aggregation of SWCNT encourage the formation of electrical pathways and reduce the number of light scatters, hence favoring the transmittance of the visible light through these materials.

In summary, transparent electrically conductive bulky polymer nanocomposites can be available by mixing the percolative concentration of SWCNT in the polymer melt, a processing method very well established in the polymer industry.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the financial support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Education (Grant MAT2005-01768) and from Comunidad de Madrid-CSIC (Grant CAM/CSIC:CCG07-CSIC/MAT-2296). M.C.G.G. is also grateful to the Ramón y Cajal Program for the support of this research.

References

- [1] Coleman JN, Khan U, Gunko YK. Mechanical reinforcement of polymers using carbon nanotubes. *Adv. Mater.* 2006; 18: 689-706.
- [2] Bauhofer W, Kovacs JZ. A review and analysis of electrical percolation in carbon nanotube polymer composites. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2009; available online.
- [3] Sandler JKW, Kirk JE, Kinloch IA, Shaffer MSP, Windle AH. Ultra-low electrical percolation threshold in carbon-nanotube-epoxy composites. *Polymer* 2003; 44: 5893-5899.
- [4] Gojny FH, Wichmann MHG, Fiedler B, Kinloch IA, Bauhofer W, Windle AH, Schulte K. Evaluation and identification of electrical and thermal conduction mechanisms in carbon nanotube/epoxy composites. *Polymer* 2006; 47: 2036-2045.

- [5] Leterrier Y, Medico L, Demarco F, Manson J-AE, Betz U, Escola MF, Olsson MK, Atamny F. Mechanical integrity of transparent conductive oxide films for flexible polymer-based displays. *Thin Solid Films* 2004; 460: 156-166.
- [6] Schmidt RH, Kinloch IA, Burgess AN, Windle AH. The effect of aggregation on the electrical conductivity of spin-coated polymer/carbon nanotube composite films. *Langmuir* 2007; 23: 5707-5712.
- [7] Sung BJ, Jo PS, Shin H, Huh J, Min BG, Kim DH, Park C. Transparent, Low-Electric-Resistance Nanocomposites of Self-Assembled Block Copolymers and SWCNT. *Adv. Mater.* 2008; 9999: 1-6.
- [8] Lima MD, de Andrade MJ, Skákalová V, Nobre F, Bergmann CP, Roth S. In-situ synthesis of transparent and conductive carbon nanotube networks. *Phys. Stat. Sol.* 2007; 1: 165-167.
- [9] Lima MD, de Andrade MJ, Bergmann CP, Roth S. Thin, conductive, carbon nanotube networks over transparent substrates by electrophoretic deposition. *J. Mater. Chem.* 2008; 18: 776-779.
- [10] Gordon RG. Criteria for choosing transparent conductors. *MRS Bull.* 2000; 25: 52-57.
- [11] Crawford GP, *Flexible Flat Panel Displays*, Wiley, Hoboken, NJ 2005.
- [12] Nogales A, Broza G, Roslaniec Z, Schulte K, Sics I, Hsiao BS, Sanz A, García-Gutiérrez MC, Rueda DR, Domingo C, Ezquerro TA. Low Percolation Threshold in Nanocomposites Based on Oxidized Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes and Poly(butylene terephthalate). *Macromolecules* 2004; 37: 7669-7672.
- [13] Hernández JJ, García-Gutiérrez MC, Nogales A, Rueda DR, Ezquerro TA. Small-angle X-ray scattering of single-wall carbon nanotubes dispersed in molten poly(ethylene terephthalate). *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2006; 66: 2629-2632.

- [14] Broza G, Kwiatkowska M, Roslaniec Z, Schulte K. Processing and assessment of poly(butylene terephthalate) nanocomposites reinforced with oxidized single wall carbon nanotubes. *Polymer* 2005; 46: 5860-5867.
- [15] Baltá Calleja FJ, García-Gutiérrez MC, Rueda DR, Piccarolo S. Structure Development in Poly(ethylene terephthalate) Quenched from the Melt at High Cooling Rates: X-ray Scattering and Microhardness Study. *Polymer* 2000; 41:4143-4148.
- [16] García-Gutiérrez MC, Hernández JJ, Nogales A, Panine P, Rueda DR, Ezquerra TA. Influence of Shear on the Templated Crystallization of Poly(butylene terephthalate)/Single Wall Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites. *Macromolecules* 2008; 41: 844-851.
- [17] Tzavalas S, Drakonakis V, Mouzakis DE, Fischer D, Gregoriou VG. Effect of carboxy-functionalized multiwall nanotubes (MWNT - COOH) on the crystallization and chain conformations of poly(ethylene terephthalate) PET in PET - MWNT nanocomposites. *Macromolecules* 2006; 39:9150-9156.
- [18] A Broad band Dielectric Spectroscopy; Kremer F, Schönhals A, Eds.; Springer: Berlin, 2002.
- [19] Jonscher, AK. The 'universal' dielectric response. *Nature* 1977; 267: 673-679.
- [20] Stauffer, D. In: Introduction to Percolation Theory; Taylor&Francis: London, 1985.
- [21] Kirkpatrick, S. Percolation and Conduction. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 1973; 45: 574-588.
- [22] Jager, KM, McQueen DH, Tchmutin IA, Ryvkina NG, Kluppel M. Electron transport and ac electrical properties of carbon black polymer composites. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 2001; 34: 2699-2707.
- [23] Connor MT, Roy S, Ezquerra TA, Baltá-Calleja FJ. Broadband ac conductivity of conductor-polymer composites. *Phys. Rev. B* 1998; 57: 2286-2294.

- [24] Kilbribe BE, Coleman JN, Fraysse J, Fournet P, Cadek M, Drury A, Hutzler S, Roth S, Blau WJ. Experimental observation of scaling laws for alternating current and direct current conductivity in polymer-carbon nanotube composite thin films. *J. Appl. Phys.* 2002; 92: 4024-4030.
- [25] Barrau S, Demont P, Peigney A, Laurent C, Lacabanne C. Dc and ac conductivity of carbon nanotubes-polyepoxy composites. *Macromolecules* 2003; 36: 5187-5194.
- [26] Landi BJ, Raffaele RP, Heben MJ, Alleman JL, Van-Derveer W, Gennett T. Single Wall Carbon Nanotube - Nafion Composite Actuators. *Nano Lett.* 2002; 2: 1329-1332.
- [27] Benoit JM, Corraze B, Lefrant S, Blau WJ, Bernier P, Chauvet O. Transport properties of PMMA-carbon nanotubes composites. *Synth. Met.* 2001; 121: 1215-1216.
- [28] Linares A, Canalda JC, Cagiao ME, García-Gutiérrez MC, Nogales A, Martín-Gullón I, Vera J, Ezquerro TA. Broad-Band Electrical Conductivity of High Density Polyethylene Nanocomposites with Carbon Nanoadditives: Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes and Carbon Nanofibers. *Macromolecules* 2008; 41: 7090-7097.
- [29] Kymakis E, Alexandou I, Amaratunga GA. Single-walled carbon nanotube-polymer composites: Electrical, optical and structural investigation. *Synth. Met.* 2002; 127: 59-62.
- [30] Grunlan JC, Mehrabi AR, Bannon MV, Bahr JL. Water-based single-walled-nanotube-filled polymer composite with an exceptionally low percolation threshold. *Adv. Mater.* 2004; 16: 150-153.
- [31] Grunlan JC, Liu L, Kim YS. Tunable single-walled carbon nanotube microstructure in the liquid and solid states using poly(acrylic acid). *Nano Lett.* 2006; 6: 911-915.

[32] Ramasubramaniam R, Chen J, Liu H. Homogeneous carbon nanotube/polymer composites for electrical applications. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 2003; 83: 2928-2930.

[33] Du F, Scogna RC, Zhou W, Brand S, Fischer JE, Winey KI. Nanotube networks in polymer nanocomposites: Rheology and electrical conductivity. *Macromolecules* 2004; 37: 9048-9055.

[34] Martin CA, Sandler JKW, Windle AH, SCHWARZ M-K, BAuhofer W, Schulte K, Shaffer MSP. Electric field-induced aligned multi-wall carbon nanotube networks in epoxy composites. *Polymer* 2005; 46: 877-886.

Table 1. Sample thickness (μm) for both series of nanocomposites: prepared by direct mixing of carbon nanotubes in the molten polymer (DM) and prepared by in-situ polymerization (I-SP).

% wt SWCNT	DM	I-SP
0	270	260
0.02	260	----
0.1	270	250
0.2	270	280
0.3	----	220
0.5	250	----
1.5	300	----

Figure Captions

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) of the SWCNT as received.

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM): (a) Cryogenic fractured surface of the PET/0.2 wt% SWCNT nanocomposite prepared by direct mixing. (b) Cryogenic fractured surface of the PET/0.3 wt% SWCNT nanocomposite prepared by in-situ polymerization.

Figure 3. Broad band electrical conductivity, σ (F) as a function of frequency, F, for nanocomposites prepared by direct mixing (upper panel) and nanocomposites prepared by in-situ polymerization (bottom panel), the weight % nanoadditive concentrations are labeled on the right.

Figure 4. Logarithm of the electrical conductivity versus nanoadditive weight concentration for nanocomposites prepared by direct mixing (○) and for nanocomposites prepared by in-situ polymerization (●). The continuous lines are the fitting of equation 2, according to percolation theory.

Figure 5. Comparison of the transparency of nanocomposites with 0.1 wt% of SWCNT prepared by direct mixing (left side) and by in-situ polymerization (right side). Thicknesses of nanocomposites are 270 μm and 250 μm respectively.

Figure 6. Optical transmittance (%) versus nanoadditive weight concentration for nanocomposites prepared by direct mixing (○) and for nanocomposites prepared by in-situ polymerization (●). Data with the highest transmittance correspond to the polymer matrix.

Figure 7. Optical transmittance (%) versus the logarithm of the conductivity for the two series of nanocomposites: direct mixing (○) and in-situ polymerization (●). In addition are plotted the calculated values of conductivity and transmittance for a nanocomposite prepared by DM with composition the percolation critical concentration ($\phi_c = 0.024$ wt % of SWCNT) (Δ).

Figure 1

(a)

(b)

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7